

Multiple equilibria involved in some nickel(II) mixed ligand complex systems containing catecholic and dipeptide ligands

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Multiple equilibrium studies on Ni^{II}-dopamine/dopa(A)-glycyl-L-tryosine and L-tyrosylglycine(B) systems show the formation of NiABH₂, NiABH or NiAB mixed ligand complexes. The results indicate that dopa is ambidentate, i.e. in NiABH₂ species it binds the metal ion in a glycine-like mode, while it coordinates in a pyrocatecholic mode in NiABH and NiAB complexes. Dopamine(A) binds in a pyrocatechol mode in its mixed ligand complexes. Both the dipeptide(B) ligands bind via *N*-amino and *O*-peptide groups in all the mixed ligand complexes.

Aromatic compounds bearing phenolic and carboxylic groups serve as versatile ligands to chelate toxic and nutrient metal ions in living systems. They act as non-specific ligands towards metal ions in terrestrial and aquatic systems, and most of these compounds are found in the natural environment as products of metabolic and degradation processes. Much work has been done on complexes containing catechols^{1,2}. 3,4-Dihydroxyphenylalanine (dopa) and dopamine (dopm) belong to this class of catecholic ligands and their interaction with metal ions can therefore be an important factor. The ambidentate binding of dopa has been well established^{2,3}. In contrast to dopa, dopm is capable of forming chelates through phenolic hydroxy groups. The present communication reports the multiple equilibria involved in the mixed ligand complex formation of Ni^{II} with dopm and dopa(A) in the presence of two tyrosine containing dipeptides, viz. glycyl-L-tyrosine(glytyr) and L-tyrosylglycine(tyrgly) (B). Tyrosine constitutes the *N*-terminus of endogenous analgesic peptides such as enkephalin⁴ and endorphin⁵. All the studies have been carried out by pH-titrimetry at 37° and *I* = 0.15 M (NaClO₄). The computations have been made by scogs computer program⁶.

Results and Discussion

Mixed ligand complexes of stoichiometry NiABH, NiAB, NiABH₋₁, NiA₂BH and NiAB₂ in dopm(A) systems and NiABH₂, NiABH, NiAB and NiABH₋₁ in dopa(A) systems have been assumed in different chemical models. The dopm(A) systems gave rise to the formation of NiABH and NiAB species, while in dopa(A) systems, NiABH₂, NiABH and NiAB complexes have been detected (Table 2), in addition to the various binary species due to ligands A and B (Table 1). The standard deviations in titre, σ_v falls between 0.032 and 0.043.

Table 1. Stability constants for the proton and Ni^{II} complexes

Temp. = 37°, *I* = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄)

Parameter	Ligands ^a			
	dopm ^a	dopa ^a	glytyr ^b	tyrgly ^b
log β _{HA}	11.48(4)	11.45(5)	7.84(4)	7.82(7)
log β _{H₂A}	21.61(3)	21.10(4)	10.66(6)	10.19(10)
log β _{H₃A}	30.34(4)	29.73(6)	—	—
log β _{H₄A}	—	32.38(8)	—	—
log β _{NiAH₂}	—	25.93(9)	—	—
log β _{NiAH}	18.12(2)	—	—	—
log β _{NiA}	9.66(12)	10.84(6)	4.23(4)	4.12(7)
log β _{NiA₂H₄}	—	51.16(11)	—	—
log β _{NiA₂H₃}	—	43.36(23)	—	—
log β _{NiA₂H}	26.07(4)	—	—	—
log β _{NiA₂}	—	—	7.54(5)	7.99(10)
log β _{NiA₂H₋₂}	—	—	-8.72(6)	-7.93(10)
log β _{NiA₋₂}	—	—	10.44(5)	—

^aLigands glytyr and tyrgly become secondary ligands B in the mixed ligand systems.

^aRef. 10, ^bRef. 9.

The NiABH species has been detected in all the title ternary systems under study. Since no protonated binary species have been detected in Ni^{II}-glytyr and tyrgly(B) systems⁷ and such species have been reported only in Ni^{II}-dopm/dopa(A) binary systems⁸ (Table 1), it can be concluded that in the NiABH species the extra proton is attached with dopm/dopa(A) ligand. The log K_{NiABH}^{NiB} values in dopm(A) systems (Table 2) bear favourable comparison with the log β_{NiAH} value in Ni^{II}-dopm(A) system⁸ (Table 1), where dopm(A) with its amino group protonated binds the metal ion in a pyrocatechol-mode. Again, the log K_{NiABH}^{NiAH} values in dopm(A) systems (Table 2) correspond to the bidentate binding of glytyr and tyrgly(B) via *N*-amino and *O*-peptide groups. Thus the metal ion is four-coor-

minated in the NiABH species in the dopm(A) systems. The comparable $\log \beta_{\text{NiABH}}$ values in dopm and dopa(A) systems (Table 2) show that in both the systems, in the NiABH species the same type of binding is involved, i.e. the extra proton is attached with the amino group of (A) ligands and the protonated dopm/dopa(A) ligand binds the metal ion in a pyrocatechol mode and the dipeptide(B) binds via *N*-amino and *O*-peptide atoms. The more positive $\Delta \log K_{\text{NiABH}} (= \log \beta_{\text{NiABH}} - \log \beta_{\text{NiAH}} - \log \beta_{\text{NiB}})$ values obtained in all the mixed ligand systems compared to the statistical values⁹ show higher stability for NiABH compared to NiAH or NiB.

Table 2. Stability constants for the mixed ligand complexes in the Ni^{II}-A-B systems

Temp. = 37°, *I* = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄)

Parameters	dopm (A)		dopa (A)	
	Ligand B		Ligand B	
	glytyr	tyrgly	glytyr	tyrgly
$\log \beta_{\text{NiABH}_2}$	—	—	30.61(6)	—
$\log \beta_{\text{NiABH}}$	21.91(8)	22.14(9)	22.81(7)	22.29(9)
$\log \beta_{\text{NiAB}}$	—	13.58(12)	14.17(11)	14.04(12)
$\log K_{\text{NiABH}_2}^{\text{NiB}}$	—	—	26.38	—
$\log K_{\text{NiABH}_2}^{\text{NiAH}_2}$	—	—	4.68	—
$\Delta \log K_{\text{NiABH}_2}$	—	—	0.45	—
$\text{p}K_{\text{NiABH}}^{\text{H}}$	—	8.56	8.64	8.25
$\log K_{\text{NiABH}}^{\text{NiB}}$	17.68	18.02	18.58	18.17
$\log K_{\text{NiABH}}^{\text{NiAH}_2}$	3.79	4.02	—	—
$\Delta \log K_{\text{NiABH}}$	-0.44	-0.10	—	—
$\log K_{\text{NiAB}}^{\text{NiB}}$	—	9.46	9.94	9.92
$\log K_{\text{NiAB}}^{\text{NiA}}$	—	3.92	3.33	3.20
$\Delta \log K_{\text{NiAB}}$	—	-0.20	-0.90	-0.92

The NiABH₂ complex species has been detected only in the Ni^{II}-dopa(A)-glytyr(B) system, where the value of $\log K_{\text{NiABH}_2}^{\text{NiB}}$ (Table 2) bears favourable comparison with the $\log \beta_{\text{NiAH}_2}$ value in Ni^{II}-dopa(A) system⁸ (Table 1). In the NiAH₂ dopa species, dopa(A) with its phenolic hydroxo groups protonated binds the metal ion in a glycine-like mode. This shows that in the Ni(AH₂)B species in the mixed ligand system also, both the protons reside with dopa(A) ligand and the protonated ligand binds the metal ion in a glycine-like mode. The $\log K_{\text{NiABH}_2}^{\text{NiAH}_2}$ value of 4.68 corresponds to the bidentate binding of glytyr(B) via *N*-amino and *O*-peptide groups. The positive $\Delta \log K_{\text{NiABH}_2} (= \log \beta_{\text{NiABH}_2} - \log \beta_{\text{NiAH}_2} - \log \beta_{\text{NiB}})$ value of 0.45 shows that glytyr(B) ligand adds on to NiAH₂ rather than to the aquated metal ion.

The NiAB type of species has been detected in the Ni^{II}-dopm(A)-tyrgly(B) and Ni^{II}-dopa(A)-glytyr and -tyrgly(B) systems. The $\log K_{\text{NiAB}}^{\text{NiB}}$ value of 9.46 in the Ni^{II}-dopm(A)-tyrgly(B) system is comparable with the $\log K_1$ value of

9.66 for NiA dopm(A) species⁸, where dopm(A) binds the metal ion in a pyrocatechol mode. This shows that in the mixed ligand species also, dopm(A) binds in a pyrocatechol mode. Again, the $\log K_{\text{NiAB}}^{\text{NiA}}$ value of 3.92 in dopm(A) system corresponds to the bidentate binding of tyrgly(B) via *N*-amino and *O*-peptide groups. Thus, Ni^{II} is four-coordinated in the NiAB dopm(A) species. The $\log \beta_{\text{NiAB}}$ values in the Ni^{II}-dopa(A)-glytyr and -tyrgly(B) systems are comparable to those in the Ni^{II}-dopm(A)-tyrgly(B) system (Table 2). This shows that dopa(A) binds in a pyrocatechol mode and the dipeptide(B) is bidentate in the NiAB species in the former two systems. The slightly higher value of $\log \beta_{\text{NiAB}}$ in the Ni^{II}-dopa(A)-glytyr(B) system compared to that in the Ni^{II}-dopa(A)-tyrgly(B) can be accounted as due to the presence of the bulky aromatic group at the C-terminal residue of glytyr(B). The $\Delta \log K_{\text{NiAB}} (= \log \beta_{\text{NiAB}} - \log \beta_{\text{NiA}} - \log \beta_{\text{NiB}})$ value of -0.20 in the dopm(A) system is more positive compared to the statistical value⁹, demonstrating higher stability of NiAB species compared to NiA or NiB. However, the values obtained for this parameter in the mixed ligand systems involving dopa(A) do not deviate much from the statistical value.

The NiABH₂ species in dopa(A) system has been found to be maximum favoured at a comparatively lower pH, accounting to a maximum of ~50% in the 1 : 1 : 1 solution of Ni^{II}-dopa(A)-glytyr(B). The formation of NiABH in both dopm/dopa(A) systems occurs above pH 6 and more than 30% of the total Ni^{II} is found to be present in its form. A ~15% of Ni^{II} is found to be present in the form of NiAB species in both dopm and dopa(A) systems around pH 8. In order to demonstrate these trends, the species distribution

Fig. 1. Speciation curves of 1 : 1 : 1 Ni^{II}-dopa(A)-glytyr(B) : (1) unbound metal, (2) NiAH₂, (3) NiA, (4) NiB, (5) NiABH₂, (6) NiABH and (7) NiAB. Curves for NiA₂H₄, NiA₂H₃, NiB₂, NiB₃ and NiB₂H₂ could not be drawn due to their low concentrations

diagram obtained in the Ni^{II}-dopa(A)-glytyr(B) is given in Fig. 1.

Experimental

All the ligands used were Sigma products. Stock solutions of nickel perchlorate and other reagents were prepared and estimated as described earlier¹⁰. The pH-titrations was carried out using an ECIL pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH unit). The stability constants of the complexes were computed from titrations in which the total concentrations of metal, ligand A and B were in 1 : 1 : 1 ratio. Calculations were done using SCOGS computer program⁶ on a NEXUS XT4AT6 computer, fixing the auxiliary data obtained at the same experimental conditions in the Ni^{II}-dopm/dopa(A)⁸ and Ni^{II}-dipeptide(B) systems⁷ as non-refinable parameters.

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